

Algebraic vs. transcendent approach to Legendre and Feigenbaum constants

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Abstract:

Legendre module λ , Feigenbaum constant δ_F and α_F and modular units $g(a)$ depend on principal ideals of complex multiplication (CM). The Hermite problem for cubic irrationalities is treated by quaternary continued fractions (QCF). The inflection point condition on elliptic curves (IPC) is generalized to CM via quaternary continued fractions (QCF) showing λ - invariances and a tower of modular units $g(a)$. Statistical λ - fluctuations on d-dimensional hypersurfaces S_d ($d \leq 5$) shape a pseudo-periodic contour. A transcendent vs. algebraic treatment of δ_F , α_F and λ depends on topological entropy. Cycles on disk segments S_d yield $\delta_F \alpha_F^2 = const$ in agreement with computation.

1.Introduction

Invariants of an elliptic curve E_λ are algebraic number lying in $\mathbb{K}(\partial)$ for a non-trivial endomorphism $\text{End}(E_\lambda/\mathbb{K}) \cong \{M \in \mathbb{C} : M\mathbb{L} \subset \mathbb{L}\} \neq \mathbb{Z}$ and a lattice $\mathbb{L} \in \mathbb{K}(\partial)$ and cubic irrationality ∂ . Complex multiplication (CM) is singular if M belongs to an imaginary quadratic field $M \in \mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{\Delta}]$. Principal ideal domains discussed here with class number one $h_\Delta=1$ exist only in cases $e_\Delta=(1,2,3)$ with discriminants $\Delta=-\{(7,1,19,43,67,163),4,3\}$.

The present paper calculates the Legendre module λ (cross ratio) in dependence on the inflection point condition on elliptic curves (IPC) and Poncelet closure [1]. The transcendental entire function $\sigma(u) = e^{\int_{\mathcal{C}(u)} dv \zeta(v)}$ depends only on endpoints of contour $\mathcal{C}(u)$. Collineated quadruples

$$\wp_k \leftarrow \wp_{k-1} + a_{1k} \wp_{k-2} + a_{2k} \wp_{k-3} + a_{3k} \wp_{k-4} = \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{a}) \{ \wp_{k-1}, \wp_{k-2}, \wp_{k-3}, \wp_{k-4} \}$$

with $\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{a})$ from (13.1) entering (12.9) yield four CM layers $M_s \in \mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{\Delta}]$ and

complex Legendre module $\lambda \in \mathbb{C}$. As a statistical product of modular units $g(a)$,

$a \in \mathbb{Q}^2$ [2] λ depends on a sum of contours $\mathcal{C}(u)$. One-dimensional chaotic maps

are transformed to IPC generalizing [3]. Mandelbrot maps require d- dimensional

complex spaces \mathbb{C}^d to picture cardioids. A complex parameter $c \in \mathbb{C}$ and complex Feigenbaum constants $\delta_F \in \mathbb{C}$ is related to complex λ .

For a normal field $\mathbb{N}[\sqrt{\Delta}] = \mathbb{K}[\partial]\mathbb{K}'[\partial]\mathbb{K}''[\partial]$ in case of $h_\Delta = 1$ and $e_\Delta = (1,2,3)$ invariants $j \in \mathbb{N}$ are reducible to a cubic polynomial

$$f^3(\omega) + 2E f^2(\omega) + 2F f(\omega) + 2 = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

for the Weber- Schlaefli invariant $f(\omega) = 1^{48} \frac{\eta(\frac{\omega+1}{2})}{\eta(\omega)}$ [4] with Dedekind eta

function $\eta(\omega)$, Weber invariant $\gamma_2 = \sqrt[3]{j} = \frac{f^{24}(\omega) - 2^4}{f^8(\omega)} \in \mathbb{N}$ and integers

$(E, F) = (0,0), (1,1), (0,-1), (1,0), (1,-1), (3,2) \in \mathbb{N}^2$. The square of the Dedekind eta

function $\eta^2(\omega) = \frac{\prod g(a\omega)}{\prod g(a'\omega)}$ depends on an infinity of representations in terms

modular units (4.1). This allows a modular, quadratic Hermite substitution of (1.1) for $h_\Delta = 1$.

A $f(\omega)$ cycle with $f^{b^{2^k}}(\omega) = 1$ has complex k roots at $k_{CS} = H_{CS} + \frac{2\pi i n}{\ln 3}$ with

Hausdorff dimension of Cantor set $H_{CS} = \log_3 2$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$. A generator b^{2^k} exists for first four prime Fermat number congruences [5] for $b=3^k=2$.

$f(\omega)$ fluctuations change λ , quarter periods $K(\lambda)$ and $K'(\lambda)$ for CM fields $M_s \mathbb{L}$. A (u, λ) description is simpler [6] than a (u, K, K') description.. The aim is to linearize $K \simeq \lambda$ on disk segments $S_d [M_d \mathbb{L}] \in \delta \mathbb{X}$ for a cubic $K(\lambda)$ equation.

First the N^{th} Landen transform of real values $K(\lambda)$ with Legendre module λ [7] yields $\lambda(\delta \wp) \rightarrow 0$ for $N \rightarrow \infty$.

$$q = 1^{\frac{iK'}{2K}} = e^{2^{-N} \ln \lambda_N + 2^{2-N} \ln 2} \quad (1.2)$$

IPC with $u = a\omega \in \mathbb{L}$ $a \in \mathbb{Q}^2$ and QCF creates cycles and a CM field $M_s (s=1, \dots, 4)$ via iterating $K_d[\lambda_d]$ on S_{d-1}

$$u[K_d[\lambda_d[g[u, M_d \mathbb{L}[K_{d-1}[\lambda_{d-1}[\dots]]]]]] \in M_d \mathbb{L}_d.$$

A lattice recursion $\mathbb{L}_d[\mathbb{L}_{d-1} \dots \mathbb{L}_1]$ is seen as equivalent to d -dimensional cardioid of Mandelbrot sets.

$f(\omega)$ fluctuations in (1.2) enter via $\lambda \lambda' = 2^4 / f^{24}(\omega)$ ($\lambda' = 1 - \lambda$). Unimodular collineated quadruples contain CM fields M_{s-1} . For Poncelet closure cycles

$\lambda(\delta \wp = \wp(u) - \wp(u'))$ depends on a product of modular units $g(a, \mathbb{L}_d)$. The present paper discusses a complex case $\lambda(\delta \wp) \in \mathbb{C}$ for a pencil $\{E_\lambda\}$ with fluctuating

complex $f(\omega)$ on $S_d [M_d\mathbb{L}]$. For a definite supremum algorithm λ is proportional to changes of topological entropy h_t . Accordingly, Legendre module and Feigenbaum constant get complex for cyclotomic and modular units on \mathbb{S}^1 in dependence on powers $f^N(\omega)$. A center of origin of \mathbb{C} develops as nested disks. $\lambda(\delta\wp)$ reads [1,8]

$$\lambda(\delta\wp) = (ijkl) = \frac{(ij)(kl)}{(ik)(jl)} = \frac{\sigma_{ij}\sigma_{kl}}{\sigma_{ik}\sigma_{jl}} \quad (1.3)$$

where $(ij)=p(u_i)-p(u_j)$, $i \rightarrow p(u_i)=\gamma\wp(u_i)$, $\sigma_{ij} = \sigma(u_i+u_j)\sigma(u_i-u_j)$, $\gamma \in GL(2, \mathbb{C})$ and invariant with respect to $u_i \rightarrow u_s - u_i$ where $u_s = \frac{1}{2}(u_1+u_2+u_3+u_4)$

$$\lambda(\delta\wp) = e^{\int_C (ijkl) dv\zeta(v)} \quad (1.4)$$

$\lambda(\delta\wp)$ depends only on endpoints of a 4-point contour $C(ijkl)$

$$C(ijkl)=(u_i+u_k, u_i+u_j) \oplus (u_i-u_k, u_i-u_j) \oplus (u_j+u_l, u_k+u_l) \oplus (u_j-u_l, u_k-u_l).$$

4-point cross ratio (1.4) and IPC flex point product A_{\square} are $\exp(\int_{C-C'} dv\zeta(v))$

but for topological different contour $C-C'$ being equivalent in equianharmonic case (EQ). Statistical contour $C-C'$ collineated by $M(\mathbf{a})u$ in IPC yield a CM

lattice $M_s\mathbb{L}$. Added points as a fractional substitutions of roots in (12.4) are related to $f(\omega) \rightarrow \gamma\wp f(\omega)$ in (1.1). The aim of the present paper is to show that the $\lambda(\delta\wp)$ exponent $\int dv\zeta$ depends on λ itself via QCF shifts of $C-C'$ endpoints. A contour dependence of $\lambda(\delta\wp)$ is discussed as a Tschirnhaus resolvent $\{f(\omega)\}$ of (1.1) [9] for complex $f(\omega)$ in $M_d\mathbb{L}$ with $M_d=1, M_s, s=1,2,3,4$. The generalized principal ideal theorem of complex multiplication [10] predicts an equivalence $\lambda_{Ng^2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbb{L}) \simeq \delta_F \alpha_F^2$ if a generator exists of a number theoretic transform (NTT) as a tower of modular units.

IPC is formulated as a matrix of fourth order suffering unimodular collineations as QCF on a Riemann surface \mathbb{X}_d of genus d reducible to a torus.

2. Universal covering

Corollary 1: Nested disks $S_d[M_d\mathbb{L}]$ of toroidal layers with $\binom{d-2}{2}$ independent parameter constitute a generalized Riemann surface $\delta\mathbb{X}$ of genus $d \leq 5$. Due to IPC $\delta\mathbb{X}$ consists of four CM layers ($M_d=1, M_s, s=1,2,3,4$) as rational self-maps from nested S_d to nested spheres $S^2(\mathbf{a}_i, p_i)$ with $i=1, \dots, 5$, $\mathbf{a}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and p_i the power of a point of origin with respect to the sphere. $S_d \in \mathbb{C}^d$ are centered around poles $k_{CS} =$

$H_{CS} + \frac{2\pi i n}{\ln 3} u_p \notin \mathbb{Q}M_d\mathbb{L}$. The uniformization parameter on $\delta\mathbb{X}$ layers

$\sum_{d=1,\dots,5} \langle f^3(\omega) - \overline{f^3(\omega)} \rangle u_k^{(d)} + \lambda_3 \chi(E)$ depends on fluctuations of (1.1) where $u_k^{(d)} \in \mathbb{C}^d$ using (6.4).

Proof: Periodic cycles of a map are cyclotomic units continuable to modular units on lattice positions. A disk segment $S_d [M_d\mathbb{L}]$ embedded in lattice $M_d\mathbb{L}$ is equivalent to a cardioid of a Mandelbrot: S_d uniformized by a Poincaré disk is affected by chaotic tessellation. Diffusion of $u=Iz$ ($z \in [0,1]$) with $\tau = \frac{l^2}{4\pi\mu} \frac{K'}{K} \in \mathbb{L}(\mu$ thermal conductivity) is depends on orbiting time τ where the memory implies completed orbits as lattice positions.

Point addition on E_λ creates a solvable quartic polynomial on \mathbb{X}_2 reducible to Weierstrass normal form. A Riemann surface \mathbb{X}_d ($d=2$) of two layers 0,1 with modular invariant differential $D_s = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial u_0} \frac{\partial}{\partial u_{0'}} \frac{\partial}{\partial u_1} \frac{\partial}{\partial u_{1'}} \right) \sigma(u)\sigma(u')|_{u' \rightarrow u}$ consists of four layers u_s with 0,1,0',1' [11]. The Hurwitz automorphism theorem $\sum_{i=1}^w 1 - r_i^{-1} = \chi(\mathbb{X}_0) = 2$ [12] prescribes four layers as a tiling of the torus with four branch points $r_i=\{2,2,2,2\}$ or three branch points $r_i=\{2,3,6\}$, $\{2,4,4\}$ or $\{3,3,3\}$. Here $\chi(E)$ is the Euler- Poincaré characteristic of a line bundle with alternating form E of genus d [13] [14]. The branched covering can be visualized as a tiling of the Euclidean plane by triangles with angles π/r_1 , π/r_2 and π/r_3 as hexagonal or quadratic lattices. The number of $\delta\mathbb{X}$ branch points w is identical to the number of generators $(\alpha, \beta) = 1^{\frac{1}{r_i}}$ as rational self- maps $L = \alpha u + \beta$ of the torus to itself (Lattés map).

$\delta\mathbb{X}$ consists of a direct sum of lattices $M_d\mathbb{L}_d$ in $\{\mathbb{X}_1(1) \cup \mathbb{X}_2\}$, $\{\mathbb{X}_1(1) \cup \mathbb{X}_2 \cup \mathbb{X}_2\}$, $\{\mathbb{X}_1(1) \cup \mathbb{X}_1(M_0) \cup \mathbb{X}_1(M_1) \cup \mathbb{X}_1(M_0') \cup \mathbb{X}_1(M_1')\}$, $\{\mathbb{X}_2 \cup \mathbb{X}_2\}$, $\{\mathbb{X}_1(M_0) \cup \mathbb{X}_1(M_1) \cup \mathbb{X}_1(M_0') \cup \mathbb{X}_1(M_1')\}$. The Weber- Schottky problem

\mathbb{X}_d for $d=3,4,5$ predicts $\binom{d-2}{2} = (0,1,3)$ independent Lagrange parameter [15].

3d-3 Fenchel- Nielsen coordinates are equivalent to rotation angles of $d-1$ spheres situated within a given sphere. An arbitrary sphere $S^2\{x^2 + \mathbf{x}_i \mathbf{a}_i = p_i\}$ is indexed by \mathbf{a}_i and p_i , the power of a point of origin with respect to the sphere at inversion,.

Maximal five independent spheres ($i=1,\dots,5$) $S^2(\mathbf{a}_i, p_i)$ require $\det(\mathbf{a}_i, p_i, 1) = 0$ leading to a determinant of fourth order for index permutations $\pi(i,j)$

$$\det A[\delta a, \delta p] = \prod_{\substack{i \neq j \\ \pi(i,j)}} \det(a_i - a_j, p_i - p_j) = 0 \quad (2.1)$$

The dimension of δX is proportional to the number topological paths connecting disks S_d or spheres $S^2(\mathbf{a}_i, p_i)$.

The Kronecker- Weber- Hilbert theorem (KWHT) consists in generating cyclotomic fields and cyclic field extensions as a pseudo-cyclic component in λ . NTT exists for congruences of quadruple iteration indices 2^{2^k} . The Feigenbaum constants δ_F and α_F are supposed to be transcendental. However a transcendental field $\mathbb{N}[j(\sqrt{\Delta})]$ exhibits a complexity by orders of magnitude higher than an algebraic cubic field $\mathbb{K}[\partial]$ [4]. A precise numerical calculation of δ_F and α_F exhibits a [17] strong dependent on the degree of transformation N . The present paper develops an algebraic and number-theoretic approach to δ_F and α_F based on cubic irrationalities, elliptic units [18] and NTT. Elliptic units and modular invariants are transcendental for number fields $\mathbb{N}[j(\sqrt{\Delta})]$ as well algebraic in $\mathbb{K}[f(\sqrt{\Delta})]$ with elliptic invariant j and Weber- Schlaefli invariant $f(\sqrt{\Delta})$ [19]. For a period lattice change $-iK^2 d\omega = K \wedge dK'$. $K(\lambda)$ and $K'(\lambda)$ depend on a pair complex-conjugated units ε and $\bar{\varepsilon}$ of the normal field $\mathbb{N}[\sqrt{\Delta}]$ via $K \rightarrow \varepsilon K$ where $\varepsilon \bar{\varepsilon} = \frac{1}{2} f^3(\sqrt{\Delta})$. Then $u_k \simeq d\omega \simeq \delta f^3(\omega)$ in (1.1) with center k_{CS} of \mathbb{C} .

3. Hermite transformations

Hermite transformations [9] $F(t, x) = \frac{f'(t)}{t-x} - \frac{1}{n} f(t)$ of a polynomial

$$f(t) = \sum_{i=0, \dots, n} \binom{n}{i} a_i x^{n-i} = 0$$

express power integral bases (PIB) $1, x, \dots, x^{n-1}$ and $1, t, \dots, t^{n-1}$ rationally.

Linear substituted roots $\gamma_\varphi x_i$ of a quartic polynomial $g(x) = \square$ yield a cubic polynomial $f(z) = \square$. Root maps $(ze_1 e_2 e_3 \infty) \rightarrow (xx_i x_j x_k x_l)$ yield p.14 [7]

$$g(x) = \frac{m_i^2}{(x-x_l)^4} f(z) \quad (3.1)$$

with $x_i = \varphi(u_i)$ and $f(x_i) = m_l = (lj)(lk)(li) \forall i, j, k, l = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ where the Hermite transformation γ_φ corresponds to the Weierstrass form

$$z - e_i = \gamma_\varphi(t) \circ z \quad (3.2)$$

$$\gamma_\varphi(t) = \left| \begin{array}{cc} \frac{1}{3} f'(t) & f(t) - \frac{t}{3} f'(t) \\ -1 & t \end{array} \right|. \quad (3.3)$$

valid $\forall \gamma_\wp(t)$ with $\gamma_\wp \in \text{SL}(2, \mathbb{Z})$ [9].

The alternate expression

$$z - e \leftarrow F(t, z) = \frac{f(t)}{t-z} - \frac{1}{3}f'(t) \quad (3.4)$$

is a rational map expressing symbolically a PIB $t^i \rightarrow t_i$ [9] as a vector.

$\gamma_\wp(t)$ are inequivalent transformations leading to CM.

For $n=3$ and $\sum e_i=0$ $F(t, z)$ yield

$$z \leftarrow F(t, z) = t_0 F_1 + t_1 F_0 \text{ where } (F_0, F_1) = (a_0 z + a_1, a_0 z^2 + a_1 z + 2a_2).$$

Introducing t -dependent coefficients

$$a(t), b(t) \text{ and } c(t), a(t) = t_0 a_0, b(t) = t_0 a_1 + t_1 a_0, c(t) = 2t_0 a_2 + t_1 a_1$$

$\gamma_\wp(t) \circ z$ are subsequent iterations z_k of a quadratic map

$$z_{k+1} \leftarrow F(t, z_k) = a(t)z_k^2 + b(t)z_k + c(t) \quad (3.5)$$

with peculiarity

- (1) if $f(z_{k+1})=0$ then $\deg z_{k+1}=3$
- (2) if $f(z_{k+1}) \neq 0$ $\deg z_{k+1}=2^k$.

or in terms of elliptic units $g(a, \mathbb{L})$

- (1) if $z_{k+1}/z_k = g(a, \mathbb{L})$ then $\deg z_{k+1}=3$
- (2) if $z_{k+1}/z_k \neq g(a, \mathbb{L})$ then $\deg z_{k+1}=2^k$

Then period doubling is equivalent to multiplication of z by an elliptic unit $g(a\omega, \mathbb{L})$.

The PIB t_0, t_1, t_2 of polynomial $F(t, z)$ implies w. l. o. g. $\sum e_i=0$. Then γ_\wp are conjugate to linear, quadratic and cubic maps.

$\forall a_3$ a Mandelbrot map M_c

$$x_{k+1} \leftarrow x_k^2 + c$$

results from (3.5) by substituting with lemniscate (LE) parameter $a_0=1, a_1=t_1=0, 2a_2=c, t_0=1$ for harmonic parameter $\lambda=-1$

$$x_{k+1} \leftarrow \frac{x_{k+1}}{a}, x_k \leftarrow x_k + \frac{b}{2a} \text{ and } c \leftarrow -\frac{\Delta(t)}{4a^2(t)} \text{ where } \Delta(t) \leftarrow b^2(t) - 4a(t)c(t)$$

$\forall a_3$ a logistic map L_{t_0}

$$x_{k+1} \leftarrow t_0 x_k (1 - x_k)$$

results from (3.5) for EQ parameter $a_0=-1, a_1=a_2=0$ on a line $t_1=-t_0$ for $\lambda=1^{1/3}$.

M_c and L_{t_0} are conjugate maps

$$x_k \leftarrow t_0 \left(\frac{1}{2} - x_k \right) \text{ and } c = \frac{t_0}{2} \left(1 - \frac{t_0}{2} \right)$$

as EQ and LE limits of E_λ for a finite region t_0, t_1 on complex plane with axes t_0 and t_1 where a Hessian polynomial $H(t_0, t_1) \simeq \gamma_2$ vanishes quadratically.

Summarizing, conjugate quadratic maps M_c and L_t are conjugate to LE and EQ Hermite substitutions ($\lambda = -1$ and $1^{1/3}$) A Hermite- transform- solution of cubic roots is equivalent to Cardano 's method [9].

A second implication is that $\gamma_\wp(t)$ is isomorph to a nontrivial endomorphism of an elliptic curve E_λ over a subfield $\mathbb{K}(\partial)$ with Legendre modul λ

$\text{End}(E_\lambda/\mathbb{K}) \cong \{M \in \mathbb{C} : M\mathbb{L} \subset \mathbb{L}\} \neq \mathbb{Z}$. The Hermite transformation γ_\wp [9] has matrix elements as cubic or quadratic polynomials where $\det \gamma_\wp = f(t)$. If matrix elements of γ_\wp are cubic residues i.e. $\left[\frac{\gamma_\wp}{p} \right]_3 = 1$ then $\gamma_\wp \in \text{SL}(2, \mathbb{Z})$ represents an equivalent substitution. Then $\text{End}(E_\lambda/\mathbb{K}) \cong \text{CM}$ generates Tschirnhaus resolvents of (1.1) $j(\mathbb{L}) \leftarrow j(\gamma_\wp(t) \circ \mathbb{L})$. For class number one $h_\Delta=1$ $M \in \mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{\Delta}]$, $j(\mathbb{L}) \in \mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{\Delta}]$ the invariant $j(\mathbb{L})$ are linear $\in \mathbb{N}$. A linear j - resolvent minimizes the $f(\omega)$ degree to 72 which reduces to 3 for $h_\Delta=1$. $A[M, u, \zeta, \wp]$ yields a quartic polynomial (Appendix 1). Transforming four roots to three on $s=1, \dots, \binom{4}{3}$ layers the projection map from \mathbb{L} to sphere \mathbb{S}^2 is up to a choice of normalization or calibration known as the Weierstrass \wp -function.

For fractional substitution $\gamma[e_i]$ of second order in $e_i = \wp(\omega_i)$ one has

$$\wp(u, \omega) = \gamma[e_i] \wp_{[g]}^2(u, \omega) \quad (3.6)$$

For Jacobi functions $\text{sn}^2(u, \sqrt{\lambda})$ or elliptic functions $s(u)$ for quartic roots $(0,1,1,m) \rightarrow (e_i) = 1/3 (2-1-m, 2l-m-1, 2m-l-1)$ [3] [20] one has

$$s^2(u) = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & -1/3(e_2 - e_3) \\ 1 & 1/3(e_3 - e_2) - (e_3 - e_1)(e_1 - e_2) \end{pmatrix} \wp(u)$$

and

$$s^2(u) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 + e_3 - e_1 & e_1 - e_3 \end{pmatrix} \text{sn}^2 \left(\sqrt{e_1 - e_3} u, \sqrt{\frac{e_2 - e_3}{e_1 - e_3}} \right).$$

4. Modular units

Elliptic units [18] [21] are modular congruences in λ as modular units $g(a\omega, \mathbb{L})$ being modular-invariant Weierstrass sigma functions

$$g(a\omega, \mathbb{L}) \equiv g(a) = \Delta^{1/12} e^{-a\eta \cdot a\omega} \sigma(a\omega, \mathbb{L}) = \Delta^{1/12} e^{-\int_0^{a\omega} dv \zeta(v, M\mathbb{L})} \quad (4.1)$$

with $\boldsymbol{\eta} = \zeta(\boldsymbol{\omega}/2, \text{ML})$, $\boldsymbol{\omega} = (\omega_1, \omega_2)$, $\mathbf{a}\boldsymbol{\omega} = r\omega_1 + s\omega_2$, $\tilde{\zeta}(v) = \zeta(v) - \boldsymbol{\omega}\boldsymbol{\eta} - \frac{1}{v}$.

Klein forms $g(\mathbf{a})$ differ from Siegel functions by the square of the Dedekind eta function $\eta^2(\boldsymbol{\omega})$ which is modular [2,18,21], e.g.

$$\eta^2(\boldsymbol{\omega}) = \frac{(\frac{1}{2}0)(\frac{1}{2}0)(\frac{1}{2}0)}{(\frac{1}{3}0)(0\frac{1}{3})(\frac{1}{3}\frac{1}{3})(\frac{1}{3}-\frac{1}{3})} \quad (4.2)$$

where (\mathbf{a}) denotes $g(\mathbf{a})$. The Klein form is invariant under $\Gamma(N)$, leading to an infinity of $\eta^2(\boldsymbol{\omega})$ representations in terms of $\Gamma(N)$ and $\Gamma(N+1)$, e.g. [22].

(4.1) takes the form $g(\mathbf{a}\boldsymbol{\omega}) = \Delta^{1/12} \tilde{U}(\mathbf{a})$ with a mean value $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}$ in

$\tilde{U}(\mathbf{a}) = e^{-\tilde{\mathbf{a}}\boldsymbol{\omega}\tilde{\zeta}(\mathbf{a}\boldsymbol{\omega})}$. A determination of $\mathbf{a} = (r,s) \in \mathbb{Q}^2$ requires values of the differential operator $\frac{\partial}{\partial u}$ on $\delta\mathbb{X}$ as an undecidable Diophantine problem. Elliptic and cyclotomic units are norm-coherent numbers [10,23] defined via norms in an extension field.

For cyclotomic units $e_N(1)$ the $e_N(u) = \left(1 - 1^{u/p^N}\right)$ ratio is given by

$$\frac{e_N(u)}{e_{N+1}(u)} = \sum_{k=0, \dots, p-1} 1^{\frac{uk}{p^{N+1}}} \text{ in terms of powers } p^N \text{ generators for } \mathbf{a} \text{ of a prime } p.$$

For a congruence number $p \approx 1 + \frac{u}{N}$ the norm ratio

$$\frac{e_N(u)}{e_{N+1}(u)} \cong \frac{\left(1 + \frac{u}{N}\right)^{\binom{N-1}{2}}}{\left(1 + \frac{u}{N}\right)^{\binom{N}{2}}} = \left(1 + \frac{u}{N}\right)^{-N} \cong e^{-u}$$

tends to an N -independent value for $N \rightarrow \infty$.

Using $\wp_u - \wp_v = \frac{\sigma_{u+v}\sigma_{u-v}}{\sigma_u^2\sigma_v^2}$ the elliptic $e_N(u)$ analogue is

$$E_N^{(e)}(u) = \frac{g(u_N + u_N^{(e)})g(u_N - u_N^{(e)})}{g^2(u_N^{(e)})} \quad (4.3)$$

where $u_N^{(e)} = 1^{e/e_\Delta} \mathbf{a}\boldsymbol{\gamma}_N \boldsymbol{\omega}$, $u_N = \mathbf{a}\boldsymbol{\omega}$, $\boldsymbol{\gamma}_N \in \Gamma(N)$ [10, 24]. In terms of the

normalized \wp -function $P(u) = \left(\varepsilon \frac{\wp(u)}{\sqrt{\Delta(\mathbb{L})}}\right)^{e_\Delta}$ with a unit one has with $\varepsilon^6 \in \mathbb{K}[\partial]$

$$P(u_N) - P(\boldsymbol{\gamma}_N \boldsymbol{\omega}) = \prod_{e=0}^{e_\Delta-1} (-\varepsilon) \frac{E_N^{(e)}(u)}{g^2(u_N)} \simeq \Theta$$

generating a PIB $1, \theta, \theta^2, \dots, \theta^n$. Products over quadratic and hexagonal lattices with $e_\Delta=2$ and 3 yield $P \simeq \wp^2$ and $P \simeq \wp^3$. Regarding $\wp(u_N^{(e)})$ and $\wp(u_{N+1}^{(e)})$ as roots of a CM curve E_{λ_N} with

$$\lambda_N = \prod_{N \in \mathbb{N}} \frac{\wp(u_N) - \wp(u_N^{(e)})}{\wp(u_N) - \wp(u_{N+1}^{(e)})} \simeq \prod_{N \in \mathbb{N}} \frac{E_N^{(e)}(u) g^2(u_{N+1})}{E_{N+1}^{(e)}(u) g^2(u_N)}.$$

5. Addition theorem for $u, \zeta(u)$ and $\wp(u)$ on $\delta\mathbb{X}$

IPC corresponds to $\det A=0$ for $A_{ij} = \zeta(u_i + u_j)$ $i, j=1, \dots, N$ or in differential form

$\wp_j^{(i)}$ if N^2 2×2 minors $A_{ij}^{(2)}$ vanish. However a modular unit $g(a\omega)$ for N -cycles

$\eta^{2N}(\omega) = \frac{\prod g(a\omega)}{\prod g(a'\omega)}$ differs from an equidistant texture of N th order Taylor-series

for $\ln \sigma(u)$ entering the addition theorem. IPC $A[M, u, \zeta, \wp]$ holds (Appendix) for non-equidistant iterations k on E_λ .

N -fold IPC yield a determinant of order 2^{2N} being an elliptic function [25] of order 2^{2N} enabling a fast composite 2^{2N} NTT for $A_k = \{u_k, \zeta_k \text{ or } \wp_k\}$ quadruple recursion

$$A_k = M(\mathbf{a}) A_k = A_{k-1} + a_{1k} A_{k-2} + a_{2k} A_{k-3} + a_{3k} A_{k-4} \quad (5.1)$$

exposed by quaternary unimodular collineations (13.1).

QCF reduce to BCF ($a_i=0$) or CF ($a_i=a_j=0$).

Abelian cycles replace the first $A[M, u, \zeta, \wp]$ column $1 \rightarrow M_s \in \mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{\Delta}]$.

IPC recursion for universal covering $u_k = \{u_{k-1}, u_{k-2}, u_{k-3}, u_{k-4}\}$, Weierstrass zeta function $\zeta_k = \{\zeta_{k-1}, \zeta_{k-2}, \zeta_{k-3}, \zeta_{k-4}\}$ and Weierstrass \wp -function $\wp_k = \{\wp_{k-1}, \wp_{k-2}, \wp_{k-3}, \wp_{k-4}\}$

are special Euclidean group $SE(3)$ steps. A Poncelet theorem in space requires [26] four $\delta\mathbb{X}$ layers with an invariant quartic polynomial (Appendix).

Hermite's ∂ -problem treated by ternary steps (Jacobi-Perron) [27,28] is non-unique. In the present paper quaternary steps (5.1) contain periodic CF, abelian number fields and invariants λ . IPC creates pseudo-random as well pseudo-periodic combinatorial orbits.

Theorem 1: With finite statistical probability IPC creates a tower $g(\mathbf{a}) \rightarrow e^{g(\mathbf{a})}$ of modular units and Legendre modules $\lambda \rightarrow e^\lambda$ for $N \rightarrow \infty$.

Proof: $A = \{u, \zeta, \wp\}$ recursion strings suffer collineations

$$A_k = A_{k-1} + a_{1k} A_{k-2} + a_{2k} A_{k-3} + a_{3k} A_{k-4} = M(\mathbf{a}) \{A_{k-1}, A_{k-2}, A_{k-3}, A_{k-4}\}.$$

For a particular collineation $a_1=-2, a_2=1$

$$M(\vec{a}) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & -2 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & a_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

one gets

$$A_k = (A_{k-1} - A_{k-2}) - (A_{k-2} - A_{k-3}) + a_3 A_{k-4}.$$

A triple $\wp_{k-1}, \wp_{k-2}, \wp_{k-3}$ results from a root transformation γ_\wp of a certain renormalized quartic equation providing period doubling by modular units in $\mathbb{K}[\partial]$.

Then $A_k = (\lambda_k - 1)(A_{k-2} - A_{k-3}) + a_3 A_{k-4}$. Collineations of point quadruples

$$u_k \leftarrow M(\vec{a}) \{u_{k-1}, u_{k-2}, u_{k-3}, u_{k-4}\}$$

$$\zeta_k \leftarrow M(\vec{a}) \{\zeta_{k-1}, \zeta_{k-2}, \zeta_{k-3}, \zeta_{k-4}\}$$

$$\wp_k \leftarrow M(\vec{a}) \{\wp_{k-1}, \wp_{k-2}, \wp_{k-3}, \wp_{k-4}\}$$

are roots of invariant equation (12.4) for Legendre module λ_k . A pencil $\{E_\lambda\}$ for $\{u_{k-1}, u_{k-2}, u_{k-3}\}, \{\zeta_{k-1}, \zeta_{k-2}, \zeta_{k-3}\}$ is k -dependent.

For $\delta_{\wp} = \wp_{k-1} - \wp_{k-2} = \gamma g^2(u)$ invariants $(\lambda - 1)g^2(u)$ enter

$$M(a) \rightarrow (\lambda - 1)g^2(u) \oplus \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & a_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5.2)$$

If $\Pi \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & a_3 \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{\Delta}]$ is periodic the CF creates a CM layer $M_s \in \mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{\Delta}]$. Inverse collineations $M^{-1}(\vec{a})$ are unique for a principal ideal domain $h_\Delta=1$ where Δ enters e_Δ [29]. Hermite's problem of expressing ∂ in terms of ternary periodic sequences [28] formulated as QCF splits into invariants and CF and abelian quadratic fields.

For $k \rightarrow \infty$ Legendre λ_k and Feigenbaum constant δ_F get equivalent.

Four EQ points u_k of an $\gamma_\wp(t)$ -invariant equation (12.4) depend on t

$$\frac{1}{3}\{(1,0),(1,1), (1,0),(0,1)\}(\omega_1, \omega_2) = \frac{1}{3}\{(1,0),(1,-2), (1,2),(0,1)\}(\omega_1, \omega_2) \text{ or}$$

$$\frac{1}{3}\{(1,1),(1,-1),(1,0),(0,1)\}(\omega_1, \omega_2) = \frac{1}{3}\{(1,1),(1,2),(1,0),(0,1)\}(\omega_1, \omega_2)$$

leading to $a = \frac{1}{3}(\mp 1, \mp 2)(\omega_1, \omega_2)$ in terms of half-periods ω_1 and ω_2 [30]. The

cross ratio $\lambda = 1^{\frac{1}{3}}$ depends on 8 nontrivial combinations of ω_1 and ω_2 fractions for four parameters u_s .

For $a_{k+1} = T_3(a_k)$ with tent map T_3 on $I_0 = [0, \frac{1}{2}]$ and $I_1 = [\frac{1}{2}, 1]$ [6]

$$T_c(u) = (-1)^{int(cu)}(cu) \text{ mod } 1 \quad (5.3)$$

where $T_c^{\circ k}(u) = T_{c^k}(u)$ one gets $a_k = \zeta_{CS}(k)$ [5] for k^{th} map $\circ k$ with Cantor string zeta function

$$\zeta_{CS}(k) = \sum_{n \in \mathbb{N}} 2^n 3^{-(n+1)k} \quad (5.4)$$

For congruence module 2^{2^N} a $\zeta_{CS}(k)$ pole at complex k_{CS} is equivalent to

$$\sum_{k \bmod (2^{2^N} - 1)} \zeta_{CS}(k) = \oint dz \zeta_{CS}(z) = 2H_{CS} \oint \frac{dza(z+z_0)}{e^z - 1} = 2H_{CS} a(z_0).$$

6. Diffeomorphisms of the interval $I = [0, 1]$ into itself

N point addition on E_λ corresponds to nonlinear dynamics with hyperelliptic measure $\mu(dx)$ for a quartic polynomial (12.4) [7]

$$\mu_h(dx) = \frac{dx}{2K\sqrt{\Phi(x)}}. \quad (6.1)$$

in comparison to a measure for the logistic map L_c

$$\mu_l(dx) = \frac{dx}{\pi\sqrt{x(1-x)}} \quad (6.2)$$

A hyperelliptic measure (6.1) with $\deg \Phi(x) = 4$ is directly related to Jacobi theta functions $\vartheta(u, \mathbb{L})$ for quarter periods K and K' .

Lebesgue measures μ_h and μ_l differ by the ratio K/π which can be determined via an arithmetic-geometric (agM) algorithm in terms of theta constants $\vartheta(2^k \mathbb{L}) (k \in \mathbb{N})$.

Jacobi inversion for an elliptic function $x(u)$ allows to define implicitly a diffeomorphisms $\chi(x)$ on unit interval $x \in I = [0, 1]$

$$\chi(x) = \frac{1}{K} x^{-1}(\sqrt{x}) = \int_0^x \mu_h(dx) \simeq \int \frac{du}{K} + \lambda_3 \chi(E) \quad (6.3)$$

as exactly solvable chaos [7] for Euler- Poincaré characteristic $\chi(E) = 0$, Lagrange multiplier λ_3 , alternating d-form E of a line bundle of type $\text{diag}(d_i)$. Condition of d- dimensional $\delta\mathbb{X}$ reducibility to a torus $M_d \mathbb{L}$ is given by a vanishing Euler- Poincaré characteristic [8]

$$\chi(E) = \frac{1}{d!} \int_{\delta\mathbb{X}} \wedge^d c_1(E) = (-1)^d \prod_{i=1, \dots, d} d_i du_i \wedge d\bar{u}_i \quad (6.4)$$

and first Chern class $c_1(E) = \sum_{i=1}^d c_i du_i \wedge d\bar{u}_i$.

For (6.2) $\chi(x) = \sin^{-1}(x)$.

7. Legendre and Feigenbaum constant on $\delta\mathbb{X}$

Legendre $\lambda = \frac{e_{0k} - e_{0k+1}}{e_{0k+1} - e_{0k+2}}$ and Feigenbaum constant $\delta_F = \frac{c_k - c_{k+1}}{c_{k+1} - c_{k+2}}$ are equivalent

if period doubling parameter c_k and roots e_{0k} of (12.4) are equivalent on $\delta\mathbb{X}$.

$f(\omega)$ and λ experience fluctuations based on

- (1) pseudo-random point- addition on elliptic curves E_λ
- (2) γ_\wp roots shift on universal covering $\delta\mathbb{X}$.
- (3) λ - dependent exponent of λ

The algebraic unit $\frac{f(\omega)}{2^{1/3}}$ for $-\Delta=3\text{mod}8$ or equation (1.1) for Weber- Schlaefli invariant $f(\sqrt{\Delta})$ can be transformed by an infinite number of inequivalent quadratic Hermite substitutions γ_\wp . within the field e.g. $\partial=2^{1/3}$. The eighth power $x=f^8(\omega)$ satisfies $x^3-\gamma_2x-2^4=0$ with Weber invariant $\gamma_2 = \frac{f^{24}(\omega)-2^4}{f^8(\omega)} \cdot f(\omega)$ fluctuations transmit to x - and χ -fluctuations due to (3.2)

$$\delta\chi = \delta \int \frac{dx}{\sqrt{\Phi(x)}} \simeq (\delta x + \dots + \delta x^4) \simeq \delta f^8(\omega) + \dots + \delta f^{32}(\omega)$$

A transform $r_N(x)$ of degree N [30]

$$x_{k+1} = r_N(x_k) \tag{7.1}$$

transforms (1.1) into an infinite set $E, F \in \mathbb{K}(\partial)$. Cubic residues i.e. $\left[\frac{\gamma_\wp}{p}\right]_3 = 1$ in $\gamma_\wp \in \text{SL}(2, \mathbb{Z})$ and $E, F \in \mathbb{Q}$ for $h_\Delta=1$ induce chaotic tessellations of the hyperbolic plane \mathbb{H} where a flow of the bifurcation diagram is stable for a diffusive time

$$\tau = \frac{l^2}{4\pi\mu} \frac{K'}{K} \in \text{ML}.$$

Coefficients c_k in δ_F correspond to roots $e_k \in \mathbb{K}(\partial)$. Period-doubling at $k \rightarrow k+1, k+2$ are addition steps $\gamma_\wp x_k \rightarrow x_{k+1}, \gamma_\wp x_{k+1} \rightarrow x_{k+2}, \gamma_\wp c_k \rightarrow c_{k+1}, \gamma_\wp c_{k+1} \rightarrow c_{k+2}$ as invariances of (12.4) .

Theorem 2. In the N point limit $N \rightarrow \infty$ the Legendre module $\lambda_N(\delta_\wp)$ tends to the Feigenbaum constant $\delta_F \cong 4,669\dots$ on universal covering $\delta\mathbb{X}$ for pencils of elliptic curves $\{E_{\lambda_N}\}$ caused by period- doubling as a quadratic transformation $\{a\} = \frac{1}{2}\{(1,0),(0,1),(1,1)\}$ of $\sigma(u)$.

Proof: Point addition (a quartic polynomial) can be transformed to an EQ invariant $A_1^3 = A_2^3$. IPC variables u, ζ and \wp suffer homogeneity transformations M_s, M_s^{-1}, M_s^{-2} .

In case of $\sigma_3 = \frac{1}{4}$ one gets a hexagonal lattice $M_s\mathbb{L}$ with the omega-2 constant

$$\omega_e = \frac{\Gamma^3\left(\frac{1}{3}\right)}{4\pi} \cong 1.5299 \tag{7.2}$$

$A_1^3 = A_2^3$ gives for modular units $g^4\left(\frac{1}{2}(10)\right) + g^4\left(\frac{1}{2}(01)\right) + g^4\left(\frac{1}{2}(11)\right) = 0$ and

$$\lambda_{N=2} = -\frac{g^4(\frac{1}{2}(10))}{g^4(\frac{1}{2}(01))} \quad (7.3)$$

where $\{a\} = \frac{1}{2}\{(1,0),(0,1),(1,1)\}$ corresponds to period-doubling.

A modular unit with rational $a=(r,s) \in \mathbb{Q}^2$ is a \mathfrak{G} -translate

$$g(a\omega) \simeq 1^{r^2\omega_1+rs\omega_2}\mathfrak{g}_1((r\omega_1+s\omega_2)\pi,\omega) \quad (7.4)$$

of the Jacobi theta function \mathfrak{g}_1 . Then $\eta^{2N}(\omega)$ is a product of modular units $g(a\omega)$ in $\Gamma(N)$ [2,18,21].

Rational parameter a result from Diophantine equations including cubic residues

i. e. $\left[\frac{\gamma_\varphi}{p}\right]_3 = 1 \pmod{p}$. Pseudo-random values $\tilde{\zeta}(a\omega)$ are eigenvalues

$D_s\sigma(u)\sigma(u') = \tilde{\zeta}(a\omega)\sigma(u)\sigma(u')$ of the differential operator

$$D_0 = \frac{\partial}{\partial u_0} - \frac{\partial}{\partial u_0'}, D_1 = \frac{\partial}{\partial u_1} - \frac{\partial}{\partial u_1'}$$

on $\delta\mathbb{X}$ -tori and reducible hyperelliptic $\sigma(u)\sigma(u')$.

Diophantine values $\{a\}$ are viewed as Hilbert's tenth problem which is not decidable. Tessellations of \mathbb{H} are influenced by chaotic lines. The situation can be characterized by a bifurcating potential flow which is stable against small periodic motions of particles.

It is expected that $e_i \simeq 1^{2r^2\omega_1+2rs\omega_2}$ giving $e_i^{qk} = c_{0i} + c_{1i}e^{kc_{2i}}$ for (q_{10}, q_{01}, q_{11}) with $c_2 = \omega_e$. Experimentally one has $c_2 = 1.530$ [6] $\simeq \omega_e$ which yields a rough estimation for the period doubling expression (7.3) $\lambda_{N=2} = e^{w_e} \cong e^{1.5299} \cong 4.617$.

Further refinement is expected via statistics in Section 9.

8. A relation $\delta_F \alpha_F^2$ on $\delta\mathbb{X}$

Corollary 2: The quotient $\prod_{e,N} \frac{E_N^{(e)}(u)g^2(u_{N+1})}{E_{N+1}^{(e)}(u)g^2(u_N)}$ for $N \rightarrow \infty$ tends to a constant term

$$\lambda_N(\delta\wp)g^2 \simeq \delta_F \alpha_F^2$$

for generator

$$g^2 = \frac{\prod_C g^2(u_{N+1})}{\prod_{C'} g^2(u_N)}$$

Proof: A zeta function of a normal field $\zeta(z, \mathbb{N}[j(\sqrt{\Delta})])$ transforms into a zeta function of a cyclotomic field [11-13] by replacing $\eta(z)$ by 1^z . Class number $h_\Delta = 1$ differ from $h_N \rightarrow \infty$. $E_N(u)$ is the KWHT analogue of an abelian number $e_N(u)$ as

a norm coherent set. Periodic cycle maps $\gamma_\wp \circ \dots \circ \gamma_\wp = 1$ generalize generators

$$g^2 = \frac{\prod_C g^2(u_{N+1})}{\prod_{C'} g^2(u_N)} \text{ as roots of unity}$$

$$\prod_{e,N} \frac{E_N^{(e)}(u)}{E_{N+1}^{(e)}(u)} = \prod_{e,N} \frac{g^2(u_N)}{g^2(u_{N+1})} \frac{\left(\wp(u_N) - \wp(u_N^{(e)})\right)}{\left(\wp(u_N) - \wp(u_N^{(e)})\right)} = g^2 \lambda_N \quad (8.1)$$

assuming that $\wp(u_N)$ with $u_N = a\omega$ is a transformed quartic root.

For k^{th} maps $\lambda_N = \lambda_N(\delta\wp^{\circ k})$

$$\delta\wp^{\circ k} = \wp(u_N) - \wp(u_N^{(e)}) = \gamma_\wp^{\circ k} \wp = \gamma_\wp \circ \dots \circ \gamma_\wp \wp$$

and $\lambda_N = \lambda_N(\delta\wp^{\circ k}) = k\lambda_N(\delta\wp) = g^2 \lambda_N(\delta\wp)$. (Theorem 3)

Corollary 3: Chaotic plaquettes

$$U_\square = \prod_{i=1,\dots,4} U(a_i, \mathbf{a}_i) = 1 \quad (8.2)$$

with $U(a_i, \mathbf{a}_i) = e^{S(a_i)} \tilde{U}(a_i)$ (8.2) create an identity map for the simplest cycle with a finite statistical weight where $U_\square \simeq A_\square$ for EQ.

Proof: A simplest cycle [14] consists of four points at $k, k+1, k+2, k+3$ where

$$z_k = z_{k+3} \text{ OR } z_{k+1} < z_k < z_{k+2} \text{ OR } z_{k+2} < z_k < z_{k+1}$$

for an interval $I(z, z')$ where $z_k = \wp(u_k)$. Differences

$$\frac{E_N(u)}{g^2(u_N)} = z_{k+1} - z_k < z_{k+2} - z_k = \frac{E_{N+1}(u)}{g^2(u_{N+1})}$$

depend on modular units $g(a)$. A bifurcation diagram consists of $\{E_\lambda\}$ lines as interval $I_{k,k'}$. A simplest cycle is equivalent that three points z_k, z_{k+1}, z_{k+2} are on different sites of inflection lines of $\{E_\lambda\}$ as an inflection point. IPC is given by the l. h. s of (12.7) [15]. Four $M(\mathbf{a})$ collineated points depend on matrix exponential $e^{S(\mathbf{a})}$. $\exists \gamma_\wp(k, k+1): z_{k+1} = \gamma_\wp(k, k+1) z_k$ by identifying addition on E_λ as Φ - root transforming. The determinant $A[M, u, \zeta, \wp] \simeq A_\square(u_k) M(\mathbf{a})$ in (12.8) contains modular units $g(a) \simeq \frac{\prod_a g(a)}{\prod_{a'} g(a')}$ (Appendix 2-4). Collineations $M(\mathbf{a}_k)$ of u, ζ, \wp on

indices $k-1$ to $k-4$ $A_k \leftarrow A e^{S(\mathbf{a})} \leftarrow A M(\mathbf{a}_k)$ are linear transformation of fourth order

$$\sigma(u_k) \leftarrow \sigma(u_{k'}) M_{kk'}(\mathbf{a}) \leftarrow \exp\left(\int dv \zeta(v) + S(\mathbf{a})\right)$$

leading to non- commutative modular units:

$$A[M, u, \zeta, \wp] \simeq \frac{\Pi_a g(a)M(a)}{\Pi_{a'} g(a')M(a')} = \frac{\Pi_k \mathcal{U}(a_k) e^{S(a_k)}}{\Pi_k \mathcal{U}(a'_k) e^{S(a'_k)}} = \frac{\Pi_k U(a_k, \mathbf{a}_k)}{\Pi_k U(a'_k, \mathbf{a}'_k)} \quad (8.3)$$

with non-commutating 4x4 matrix exponential $U(a_k, \mathbf{a}_k) = e^{S(a_k)} \tilde{U}(a_k)$.

Sharkovskii' s theorem predicts an infinite number of simplest cycles. Modular units $g(a) \simeq g(a\omega)$ as a product of four $U(a_k, \mathbf{a}_k)$ at $k, k+1, k+1, k+3$ yield the identity map as a simplest cycle (8.2).

Theorem 3: γ_\wp - dependent products $\lambda_N \Pi g^2$ on $\delta \mathbb{X}$ are equivalent to the differential topological entropy h_t and exhibit plateaus with zero self-intersection number. The $N \rightarrow \infty$ point IPC limit $\lambda_N \Pi g^2$ is equivalent to $\delta_F \alpha_F^2$.

Proof: $\delta \mathbb{X}$ is a d-dimensional complex generalized Riemann surface for with genus $d=1, \dots, 5$. $\delta \mathbb{X}$ reduction to elliptic lattices yields a vanishing Euler- Poincaré characteristic with vanishing self- intersection number. Feigenbaum constant δ_F and Legendre module λ are equivalent if iteration steps k are period-doublings. Period-doublings are cubic roots ramifying enveloping elliptic curves $\{E_\lambda\}$. $\{E_\lambda\}$ lines are stable against period motions in $\mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{\Delta}]$ and differ by elliptic units in $\mathbb{K}[\theta]$. For cubic roots $k, k+1$ and $k+2$ one has

$$\lambda_N(\delta \wp) \simeq 1 + \left\langle \frac{\wp_{k+1} - \wp_k - \wp_{k+2} + \wp_{k+1}}{\wp_{k+2} - \wp_{k+1}} \right\rangle \simeq 1 + \delta \frac{1}{N} \sum_k \ln \delta \wp \quad (8.4)$$

where δ denotes k - variation.

Here $\delta \wp_{k+1} = \delta \gamma_\wp \circ \wp_k$ and $\delta \wp_{k+N} = \delta \gamma_\wp^{\circ N} \circ \wp_k$

A supremum- algorithm yet to be determined interrelates topological entropy

$h_t(\gamma_\wp) = \sup_{d\mu(\gamma_\wp)} h_\mu(\gamma_\wp)$, Lyapunov exponent $\lambda_L(\gamma_\wp)$ and metrical entropy $h_\mu(\gamma_\wp)$.

$$h_\mu(\gamma_\wp^{\circ N}) = \lambda_L(\gamma_\wp^{\circ N}) = 2^{-N} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \ln \gamma'_\wp(\wp_i)$$

for $N=g^k$

In view of (8.1) generator g^2 gives $\wp_{k+1} = \gamma_\wp \circ \wp_k = \gamma_\wp \circ g^2(u)$ due to (3.6).

The difference $\delta \wp$ can be written as $\delta \gamma_\wp \circ \wp_k$ because

$$z - e_i = \wp_{k+1} - \wp_{k+2} = \delta \gamma_\wp(t) \circ \wp_k$$

$$(\wp_{k+1} - \wp_{k+2})^{-1} = -\delta \gamma_\wp^{-1}(t) \circ (-\wp_k^{-1})$$

$$\lambda_N(\gamma_\wp^{\circ g^k}) = 1 - \frac{\delta}{\delta k} \langle \lambda_L(\gamma_\wp) \rangle = 1 - \frac{\partial h_t(\gamma_\wp^{\circ g^k})}{\partial k} \quad (8.5)$$

Then $\delta\wp^{\circ N} = \gamma_{\wp}^{\circ N} \delta\wp$ and $h_t(\gamma_{\wp}^{\circ g^k}) = g^k h_t(\gamma_{\wp})$ [16].

Alternatively $\delta\wp = \gamma_{\wp} g^2$ and $\lambda_N(\delta\gamma_{\wp}^{\circ N}) \simeq 1 + \delta \frac{1}{N} \sum \ln \delta g^2$.

The topological entropy h_t yields an one- dimensional optimization

$\delta g^2 = (g_k + g_{k+1})(g_k - g_{k+1})$ and $N = g_k^{g_{k+1}}$ where $g_k = g(a_k)$ which enters the deciphering algorithm of the fine structure constant in [17].

Corollary 4: $\lambda_N(\delta\wp)$ is equivalent to changes of topological entropy

$ch_t(\gamma_{\wp}^{\circ N}) \simeq NH_{CS}$. EQ curves correspond to $\gamma_{\wp}^{\circ N}$ with $N=2^k$ and $h_t(\gamma_{\wp}) = H_{CS}$.

Proof: In case of EQ γ_{\wp} is generated from an invariant $f(t)=t^3 \mp 1=0$ equivalent to $t^3 \pm 1 = \pm 2$ giving $\det(\gamma_{\wp}) = f(t) = \pm 2$.

Subsequent maps $\gamma_{\wp}^{\circ N}$ yield $N = \det(\gamma_{\wp})^k = (-1)^k \cdot 2^k$. CM curves generalize a Landen transform (1.2) to complex $\lambda(\delta\gamma_{\wp})$ as a composite algorithm having lowest complexity. A k -cycle with $k \rightarrow 2^k$ implies a congruence mod 2^k-1 which yields $N = 2^k$

Subsequent $k \rightarrow 2^k$ generate Fermat number F_k transforms. First four F_k are prime having generator b^{2^k} with $b=2$ or $b=3$ as roots of unity [18]. With

$\lambda_N(\delta\wp^{\circ N}) \simeq \frac{\partial}{\partial k} h_t(k) \simeq N \ln 2 \simeq \tilde{N} \ln 3$ one gets

$h_t(\gamma_{\wp}^{\circ b^N}) = b^N H_{CS}$ with $\lambda \rightarrow 1-\lambda$ symmetry in (8.5)

The second Feigenbaum constant α_F determines k doubling as follows [19]

$$z^{\circ 2k} = -\alpha_F z^{\circ k} \quad (8.6)$$

In view of a NT α_F is equivalent to a cyclic shift of z_{k+1} for a generator g

$$z_{k+1} = g z_k \text{ and } z_{2k} = g^k z_k.$$

(8.6) is equivalent to renormalized equations $-\alpha_F g(g(-z/\alpha_F)) = g(z)$.

The existence of the second Feigenbaum constant α_F is equivalent to a NTT with generator $g(a)$. Equivalences of Legendre module $\lambda \rightarrow 1-\lambda$ transmit to δ_F .

Computed δ_F and α_F from [20] are summarized in Table in dependence on the transformation degree N of (7.1)

N	δ_F	α_F	$\delta_F \alpha_F^2$
2	4.67	2(2.5)	29.19
3	6.08	1.93	22,64
4	7.29	1.69	20,82
5	8.35	1.56	20,32
6	9.3	1.47	20,1
7	10.2	1.41	20,28
8	10.95	1.36	20,25
10	12.37	1.29	20,58

Tabelle Relation $\delta_F \alpha_F^2$ for transformation degrees = {2-8,10} from [20]

Thus, $(\delta\wp)g^2 \simeq \delta_F \alpha_F^2$ in terms of Legendre module $\lambda_N(\delta\wp)$, Feigenbaum constant δ_F , α_F and generator g^2 can be explained by changes of topological entropy.

$N=2$ values for M_i and T_c exhibit deviations which are explained by non-uniqueness of $g(a)$ bases corresponding to either 2^1 powers of 2 or 2^1 powers of 3 both being roots of unity for the first four prime Fermat number

9. λ and δ_F statistics

IPC (12.7) can be generalized by a linear shift of $\zeta(u)$ as a σ - product depending on a N -fold direct sum in contour space C and C' generalizing $C(ijkl)$ in $\lambda = \exp(\int_{C-C'} dv\zeta(v))$ for a product $\lambda_N = \prod_{ijkl}(ijkl)$ [21] [22] due to Poncelet closure [21]. Though independent on the path between segment endpoints a statistical dependence on N and on collineations $\Pi M(\mathbf{a})$ arises. Modular and cyclotomic units yield a path dependence on a complex k - contour $\lambda(\delta\wp) \simeq \exp(\sum_k \int_{C-C'} dv\zeta(v))$.

With $N \ln f(\omega) \simeq H_{CS}^d$ a tower of modular units yields $1/N$ projects onto \mathbb{C}^d : In case of $N \rightarrow \infty$ the product of modular units yields a closed complex contour in k -space the exponential map $\exp(\sum_k \int_{C-C'} dv\zeta(v))$ via Stokes theorem

$$\lambda(\delta\wp) \simeq \exp\left(\sum_{kk'} \left(\delta_{kk'} \int dv_k \zeta(v_k) + \lambda \int dv_k \wedge dv'_k (\wp(v_k) - \wp(v'_k))\right)\right) \quad (9.1)$$

with CM in $d \leq 5$ disk segments S_d [$M_d \mathbb{L}$].

On genus d surfaces S_d [$M_d \mathbb{L}$] Lagrange multiplier $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$ for conditions (12.9) (8.2) and (6.4)

$$\lambda = \prod_i \exp\left(\int_{C_i} du\zeta(u) + \lambda_1 A[M, u, \zeta, \wp] + \lambda_2 (1 - U_{\square}) + \lambda_3 \chi(E)\right) \quad (9.2)$$

as Lagrange multiplier for nilpotency $N^2 = \det A[M, u, \zeta, \wp] = 0$, for simplest cycle and zero self-intersection number $\chi(E)$.

Collineations $u \rightarrow M(\vec{a})u$ changing $C(ijkl)$ into $C_M(ijkl)$ yield correlation functions $\frac{\delta}{\delta c_M} \int_C dv \zeta$ which dominate λ .

On a disk S_d one has the exact equation [23]

$$\frac{d}{d\lambda} \lambda \lambda' \frac{dK_d}{d\lambda} = \lambda \lambda' \frac{d^2 K_d}{d\lambda^2} + (1-2\lambda) \frac{dK_d}{d\lambda} = \frac{K_d}{4} \quad (9.3)$$

giving solution (1.2). Our aim is to describe a linearized and invertible $K(\lambda)$ solution as a γ_φ substitution of (1.1) leading to symmetric (u, K, K') and (u, λ) descriptions[24].

For a zero of $\lambda(\delta\varphi)$ at lattice points on $S_d [M_d\mathbb{L}]$ and a pole in derivatives (K') of K

$$\frac{d}{d\lambda_d} = \frac{i}{\sigma_s} \frac{d}{d\lambda_{d+1}} + \Lambda(u, M_{d+1}\mathbb{L})$$

the Heuman Lambda function $\Lambda(u, M_{d+1}\mathbb{L})$ tends to a constant if $K \rightarrow 0$. The surface tension σ_s reflect changes of topological entropy h_t between $S_d[M_d\mathbb{L}]$ and $S_{d+1}[M_{d+1}\mathbb{L}]$. Zeros of λ (9.3) are treated by N-oscillator solutions at $u \in M_{d+1}\mathbb{L}$

$$K_d^3 + K_d'' - \sigma_s^2(1-H^2\lambda^2)K_d = 0 \quad (9.4)$$

and

$$(1-2\lambda)K_d' - \frac{1}{4}K_d = 0 \quad (9.5)$$

K_d'' inserted into (9.3) yields both cubic equations for $K(\lambda)$ as well for $\lambda(K)$

$$(1-2\lambda)K' + \sigma_s^2 \lambda \lambda' (1-H^2\lambda^2)K - \lambda \lambda' K^3 - \frac{1}{4}K = 0$$

expanded in terms of $f(\omega)$ satisfying a cubic invariant (1.1).

Equation (9.4) splits into 1-oscillator solutions in form of Hermite polynomials

$$\frac{d^2 K}{d\lambda^2} - \lambda \frac{dK}{d\lambda} + nK = 0 \quad (9.6)$$

As a partial solution of (9.5) one has

$$K \simeq \frac{c}{(\lambda - 1/2)^{1/8}} \text{ and } K \simeq \sigma_s \sqrt{1 - H^2 \lambda^2}.$$

A linear solution $K \simeq \lambda$ requires four-components of u, ζ, φ in IPC. In this case quarter period $K \simeq \delta_F$ induces a third order phase transition for lattice configurations as a cubic K -polynomial. Simultaneously K and λ are exponential maps for a tower of modular units $g(a)$. λ can be linearized writing $g(a)$ in terms of

idempotents for $S(a)$. Equations (9.2) and (9.4) induce a discussion of flux quantization [25] in quantum statistics in [26].

10. Conclusions

Both first Feigenbaum δ_F and Legendre constant λ suffer complex fluctuations on universal covering $\delta\mathbb{X}$ and get equivalent.

Pseudo-cyclic points are searched within pseudo-random IPC on E_λ . Pseudo-cyclic variables correspond to cycles and periods of one-dimensional maps as Hermite substitutions of a cubic/quartic polynomial. The quartic polynomial (12.4) is in agreement with the Feigenbaum renormalization functional $g(z)$ [27]. A Hermite substitution γ_\wp is conjugate to M_c and to T_{t_0} as LE and EQ elliptic curves.

Iterating $u^{\circ k}$, $u^{\circ k+1}$ and $u^{\circ k+2}$ creates modular units λ_N of E_λ of a quartic polynomial (12.11).

This corresponds to a k -space $S_d \in \mathbb{C}^5$ of five independent nested disks $S_d \simeq$ spheres $S^2(\mathbf{a}, p)$ around k embedded in a \mathbb{L} . At computation disks S_d [$M_d\mathbb{L}$] correspond to cardioids of Mandelbrot set. Modular units are cyclotomic units on S_d . A relation between Lagrange multiplier λ_i corresponds to λ , $g(a)$, δ_F and α_F . The situation is equivalent to Planck units G , \hbar and c expressing physical fields with independent coupling constant G .

The second Feigenbaum constant α_F is equivalent to a generator $g(a)$ as a mean cyclic shift. The relation $\delta_F \alpha_F^2 = \text{constant}$ is valid if a generator $g(a)$ exists for arbitrary transformation degrees N in (7.1) A relation of Legendre module λ_N to modular units of modular groups $\Gamma(N)$ as Sharkovskii ordering of combinatorial dynamics [14] needs further discussion.

Appendix 1 A relation between spheres $S^2(\mathbf{a}_i, p_i)$ and collineations $M(\mathbf{a})$

Coordinates on a sphere $S^2(\mathbf{a}_i, p_i)$ depend on four parameter u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4 satisfying relations which remain valid on Riemann surfaces \mathbb{X}_g .

First Weierstrass relations of elliptic sigma functions $\sigma(u, \mathbb{L})$ with $x(u)+x(v)+x(w)=0$ and $x(u)=\sum \sigma(u_1)\sigma(u_2)\sigma(u_3)\sigma(u_4)$ are valid for $u, v, w \cong (1, S, S^2)u$ and remain valid on $\delta\mathbb{X}$ with Rosenhain relations [28]

$$2^g x[\eta](v) = \sum_{[\varepsilon]} (-1)^{\varepsilon \wedge \eta} x[\varepsilon](u)$$

$$x[\varepsilon](u) = (-1)^{(\rho+\sigma)\varepsilon'} \vartheta_{[\varepsilon]}(u_1) \vartheta_{[\varepsilon+\rho]}(u_2) \vartheta_{[\varepsilon+\sigma]}(u_3) \vartheta_{[\varepsilon-\rho-\sigma]}(u_4)$$

where $\vartheta_{[\varepsilon]}(u)$ denotes a hyperelliptic theta function with characteristics $[\varepsilon] \Rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon \\ \varepsilon' \end{bmatrix} \in F_2^{2g}$. Four- component parameter u, v, w are related to spherical triangles.

A spherical triangle of arc length' a, b, c , angles α, β, γ yields four-component parameter u, v, w with $\tan(\frac{1}{2}m_0(2\pi, a, b, c)) = ie^v$ and $\tan(\frac{1}{2}m_0(2\pi, \alpha, \beta, \gamma)) = ie^w$ via matrices [46]

$$m_0 = \frac{1}{2} \begin{vmatrix} 1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 0 & -1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & -1 \end{vmatrix} \text{ and } S_0 = \frac{1}{2} \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 \end{vmatrix}$$

One has $(u, v, w) = (1, S, S^2)u$ as three four- component variables $\cong X, Y, Z$ on \mathbb{S}^2 .

Here $S = \text{diag}(-1, 1, 1, 1)S_0$, $S^3 = 1$, $S_0^2 = 1$.

Right multiplication $u \leftarrow uM(\vec{a})$ changes contour $C(\text{ijkl})$ into $C_M(\text{ijkl})$.

An uncertainty of spheres $\mathbb{S}^2(\mathbf{a}_i, p_i)$ with respect to \mathbf{a}_i permutations in order to find a relation to $M(\vec{a})$ is enhanced by changes $u \rightarrow u + \frac{1}{2}\hat{U}\mathbb{L}$, $v \rightarrow v + \frac{1}{2}\hat{S}\hat{U}\mathbb{L}$ and $w \rightarrow w + \frac{1}{2}\hat{S}^2\hat{U}\mathbb{L}$ via a shift with a 2×4 rectangular matrix $\hat{U}_i \in \mathbb{Z} \text{ mod } 2$. Thus $1, \dots, 2^8$ substitutions leave IPC invariant. Summed up iterations u shifted by $\sum_{l=1}^{2^8} b_l S^r U \mathbb{L}$ giving in total a group $G_{2^{2^8}}$ of the order 2^{2^8} where $r = (1, 2, 3)$ and binary number b_l .

Appendix 2 Addition of $\mathbf{x}_1 = \mathbf{x}_k = \mathbf{p}(u)$, $\mathbf{x}_2 = \mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{p}(v)$ and $\mathbf{x}_3 = \mathbf{x}_{k+2} = \mathbf{p}(u \mp v)$

Three points on E_λ given by [4]

$$\wp'^2(u) = f(x) = \sum_{i=0}^3 \binom{3}{i} a_i x^{3-i} \quad (12.1)$$

yield

$$a_0(x_k + x_{k+1} + x_{k+2}) + 3a_1 = \left(\frac{\sqrt{f(x_k)} \pm \sqrt{f(x_{k+1})}}{x_k - x_{k+1}} \right)^2 \quad (12.2)$$

leading to a quadratic equation

$$4[a_0\sigma_3 + a_3][3a_0\sigma_1 + 3a_1] - [3a_0\sigma_2 - 3a_2]^2 = 0 \quad (12.3)$$

in terms of elementary symmetric polynomials

$$3\sigma_1 = \sum x_i, \quad 3\sigma_2 = \sum x_i x_j \text{ and } \sigma = x_1 x_2 x_3.$$

Points x_i ($i = 1, 2, 3 \rightarrow k, k+1, k+2$) in (12.3) are viewed as roots of a cubic polynomial

$$\tilde{f}(x) = \sum_{i=0}^3 \binom{3}{i} \sigma_i(x_1, x_2, x_3) x^{3-i}$$

Introducing $\sigma_4 = 4\sigma_1\sigma_3 - 3\sigma_2^2$ and $\sigma_0=1$ for symbolic $\sigma_i \rightarrow \sum_1^{4-i}\sum_2^i$ and $a_i = A_1^{4-i}A_2^i$ equation (12.3) transforms into

$$\Phi(y) = \sum_{i=0}^4 \binom{4}{i} a_i \sigma_i = \sum_{i=0}^4 \binom{4}{i} A_1^{4-i} A_2^i \sum_1^{4-i} \sum_2^i = 0 \quad (12.4)$$

where a_4 automatically satisfies

$$a_0 a_4 - 4a_1 a_3 + 3a_2^2 = 0 \quad (12.5)$$

Subsequent points x_k, x_{k+1}, x_{k+2} on E_λ yield a simple invariant- theoretic formulation (12.4) which introduces, however, differential equations of high complexity as Diophantine equations.

If $u=v$ then $x_1=x_2=x=p(u)$ and $x_3=p(2u)$ one gets the doubling map on E_λ [30]

$$\wp(2u) = \frac{(\wp_u^2 + g_2/4)^2 + 2g_3\wp_u}{4\wp_u^3 - g_2\wp_u - g_3} \quad (12.6)$$

An expression $\wp(2u)$ in terms of $\wp(u)$ is rational if invariants if $g_2, g_3 \in \mathbb{Z}$:

$W_1(z) = \frac{(z^2+1)^2}{4(z^3-z)}$ ($g_2=4, g_3=0$) and $W_2(z) = \frac{z(z^3+8)}{z^3-1}$ ($g_2=0, g_3=4$) which are intensively investigated.

Taylor expansions of $\det \zeta(u_i+u_j)$ on a finite difference grid $(\Delta u)^i \frac{\partial^i}{\partial u^i}$ of $\ln \sigma(u)$

where $\prod_{u_i=u+ih, 0 < i < j \leq N} \Pi(u_i - u_j) \neq 0$ yield an elliptic function of Nth order

$\frac{\prod_C \sigma(u_C)}{\prod_{C'} \sigma(u_{C'})}$ [15] [31] as matrix of derivatives $\wp_j^{(i)}$.

\wp satisfies a cubic invariant equation on S_d as a Tschirnhaus resolvent.

Then $x_1(u), x_2(v)$ and $x_3(u \mp v)$ result from Hermite substitutions of roots of a quartic invariant equation [4].

One has

$$\begin{vmatrix} \zeta'_{02} - \zeta'_{01} & \zeta'_{03} - \zeta'_{01} \\ \zeta''_{02} - \zeta''_{01} & \zeta''_{03} - \zeta''_{01} \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & \zeta'_{01} & \wp'_{01} \\ 1 & \zeta'_{02} & \wp'_{02} \\ 1 & \zeta'_{03} & \wp'_{03} \end{vmatrix} = 0 \quad (12.7)$$

identical to the flex point product

$$A_{\square}(u_k) = \frac{\wp'_1(0)\wp_1(u_0 - \sum_{i=1,2,3} u_i) \prod_{(i,j)=1,2,3} \wp_1(u_i - u_j)}{\prod_{i=1,2,3} \wp_1^3(u_0 - u_i)} \quad (12.8)$$

where $\zeta_{0i} = \zeta(u_0 - u_i)$, $\wp_{0i} = \wp(u_0 - u_i)$.

Integrating from u_0, ζ_0, \wp_0 to u_i, ζ_i, \wp_i where $\zeta_i = \zeta(u_i)$, $\wp_i = \wp(u_i)$ one has

$$A[1, u, \zeta, \wp] = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & u_0 & \zeta_0 & \wp_0 \\ 1 & u_1 & \zeta_1 & \wp_1 \\ 1 & u_2 & \zeta_2 & \wp_2 \\ 1 & u_3 & \zeta_3 & \wp_3 \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & u_0 & \zeta_0 & \wp_0 \\ 1 & u_1 & \zeta_1 & \wp_1 \\ 1 & u_2 & \zeta_2 & \wp_2 \\ 1 & u_3 & \zeta_3 & \wp_3 \end{vmatrix} \prod M(\mathbf{a}) = 0 \quad (12.9)$$

Modular units of $\Gamma(N)$ for non-equidistant and collineated iterations of IPC (12.9) are not given by a determinant $\det \zeta(u_i+u_j)$ of rank N as an addition theorem.

QCF $u_i \leftarrow \prod M(\mathbf{a}) u_i$ in (12.9) contain a λ -dependent term (5.2) which is equivalent to a quadratic field $M \in \mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{\Delta}]$ due to continued fractions $\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & a_3 \end{pmatrix} = \prod M(\mathbf{a}) =$

$\prod \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & a \end{pmatrix}$. Then (12.9) creates maximal four CM period scaled layer of

homogeneous \wp - functions with $M_s \in \mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{\Delta}]$ ($s=1,2,3,4$) on $\delta\mathbb{X}$

$$A[M, u, \zeta, \wp] = \begin{vmatrix} M_0 & u_0 & \zeta_0 & \wp_0 \\ M_1 & u_1 & \zeta_1 & \wp_1 \\ M_2 & u_2 & \zeta_2 & \wp_2 \\ M_3 & u_3 & \zeta_3 & \wp_3 \end{vmatrix} \prod M(\mathbf{a}) = 0 \quad (12.10)$$

Invariants (5.2) in (12.9) have small but finite statistical weight. The \mathfrak{S}_1 product A_{\square} in (12.7) remains valid by replacing $u_i \leftarrow \prod M(\mathbf{a}) u_i$ leading to a contour C_M .

Multiplying u by $\frac{\pi}{KK'}$, adding u and ζ - values in $A[M, u, \zeta, \wp]$ yields $A[M, u, \Lambda, \wp]$

with ζ replaced by the Heuman Lambda function $\Lambda(u) = \frac{\pi}{KK'} + \zeta(u)$.

The quartic invariant (12.4) should be related to $\det A(M, u, \zeta, \wp) = 0$ of rank four.

IPC $A[M, u, \zeta, \wp]$ is equivalent to a 5- sphere orthogonality matrix $A[\delta a, \delta p]$.

$A[\delta a, \delta p]$ relates to spherical triangles on the unit sphere \mathbb{S}^2 via the Weierstrass relation $\sum \sigma(u_0) \sigma(u_1) \sigma(u_2) \sigma(u_3)$ (Appendix 1).

Point addition $x_1 = x_k = p(u_k)$, $x_2 = x_{k+1} = p(u_{k+1})$, $x_3 = x_{k+2} = p(u_{k+2} = u_k \mp u_{k+1})$ results from substituting from four roots of an invariant equation. Fractional substitutions

$x \rightarrow F(\gamma_{\wp} \circ t, \gamma_{\wp} \circ x) \rightarrow F(t, x)$ leave elementary symmetric polynomials (12.4)

invariant. Next (12.5) is consistent with an EQ polynomial $\sigma_2=0$ leading to $\sigma_4=0$

and

$$4A_1 \sum_1 A_2^3 \sum_2^3 + A_2^4 \sum_2^4 = 0 \quad (12.11)$$

having solution $y = \frac{A_2 \sum_2}{A_1 \sum_1} = (-4)^{\frac{1}{3}}$.

Collineations will be demonstrated for EQ E_{λ} leading to M_c , L_r and $SE(1)$

dynamics of the Lyapunov exponent. Invariant equation (12.11) is a conjugate

map to EQ $\lambda=1^{\frac{1}{3}}$.

Appendix 3 Transition from robot dynamics to chaotic dynamics

Unimodular collineations $M(\mathbf{a})$ are generalized to n dimensions as continued fractions (CF) for $n=1$, bifurcating continued fractions (BCF) for $n=2$ and chaotic continued fractions (CCF) or quaternary continued fractions (QCF) for $n=3$

$$M(a_n) = \hat{t}_{n+1} + \begin{pmatrix} 0_{1,n} & 0 \\ 0_{n,n} & a_n^T \end{pmatrix} \quad (13.1)$$

with a zero matrix $0_{n,m}$ of n rows and m columns, $a_n=(a_1, \dots, a_n)$, a cyclic matrix \hat{t}_{n+1} of order $n+1$

($\hat{t}_{n+1}^{n+1} = 1, \hat{t}_{n+1} \hat{t}_{n+1}^T = 1$). Introducing the exponential map

$$t_{n+1}^T M(a_n) = G(R, a_n) = \begin{pmatrix} R & a_n \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1_{n,n} & a_n^T \\ 0_{1,n} & 1 \end{pmatrix} = e^{S(a_n)}. \quad (13.2)$$

for $S(a_n) = \begin{pmatrix} R & a_n \\ 0_{n,1} & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ satisfying $S^4 - R^2 S^2 = 0$ and $R^2 < 0$

Unimodular collineations $M(\mathbf{a})$ result from a cyclic shift of $G(R, \mathbf{a})$ for special Euclidian $SE(3)$ group and variables $x = (\mathbf{a}, 1) \in \mathbb{S}^2(\mathbf{a}, p)$.

Nilpotent N_0 ($N_0^2 = 0$) and idempotent P_ρ for $\rho=0, \mp$ ($P_\rho^2 = P_\rho$) are

$$N_0 = \frac{1}{R^2} S^2 (R - S^2) \text{ and } P_0 = 1 - \frac{S^2}{R^2}, P_\pm = \frac{1}{2R^3} S^2 (R \mp S).$$

$M(\mathbf{a})$ is given by

$$\det M(a) = \det e^S = \det R = \det(P_0 + N_0 + e^{-R} P_+ + e^R P_-)$$

and

$$e^S = P_0 + N_0 + e^{-R} P_+ + e^R P_-$$

An $M(\mathbf{a}) - G(R, \mathbf{a})$ isomorphism of collineation $M(\mathbf{a})$ and $SE(3)$ steps in $\mathbb{S}^2(\mathbf{a}, p)$

requires four steps $\prod_{k=1, \dots, 4} R_k > 0$ where

$$\prod_{k=1}^4 \begin{pmatrix} R_k & \mathbf{x} \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} R_1 R_2 R_3 R_4 & R_1 R_2 (R_3 + 1) \mathbf{a} + (R_1 + 1) \mathbf{a} \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

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